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PROBLEMS OF THE CURRENT COMPLIANCE CONTROL SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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ANNOTATION

The article is dedicated to analyzing the current state of the compliance control system in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the context of anti-corruption efforts. The author highlights key issues that limit the effectiveness of the existing model: the absence of a unified codified law on compliance, institutional weaknesses of compliance units and the lack of internal control methodologies, a shortage of qualified personnel, insufficient digitalization of processes, as well as low legal awareness and public perception of compliance. Based on a comparative analysis with international practices (USA, UK, France, Germany, Singapore, Japan), it is demonstrated that the successful implementation of compliance systems is ensured by the presence of a unified regulatory framework, institutional independence, digital tools, professional training of personnel, and a developed ethical culture. The article emphasizes the need to adapt international standards (ISO 37001, anti-corruption conventions, EU experience) to national conditions. It concludes that regulatory strengthening, institutionalization of compliance mechanisms, development of human resources and digital platforms, as well as raising legal awareness and ethical motivation, are key prerequisites for establishing a sustainable and effective compliance control system in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: compliance control, anti-corruption, legal culture, digitalization, institutional mechanisms, Republic of Uzbekistan.

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**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИДА АМАЛДАГИ КОМПЛАЕНС-НАЗОРАТ
ТИЗИМИДАГИ МУАММОЛАР**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақола Ўзбекистон Республикасида коррупцияга қарши курашиш контекстида комплаенс назорати тизимининг ҳозирги ҳолатини таҳлил қилишга бағишланган. Муаллиф амалдаги модель самарадорлигини чекловчи асосий муаммоларни таъкидлайди: комплаенс бўйича ягона жамланган қонуннинг мавжуд эмаслиги, комплаенс бўлинмаларининг институционал заифлиги ва ички назорат методологияларининг йўқлиги, малакали мутахассислар танқислиги, жараёнларнинг етарли даражада рақамлаштирилмаганлиги, шунингдек жамиятда ҳуқуқий маданият ва комплаенсга бўлган муносабатнинг пастлиги. АҚШ, Буюк Британия, Франция, Германия, Сингапур ва Япония каби хорижий амалиётлар билан солиштирма таҳлил асосида кўрсатиладики, комплаенс тизимларини муваффақиятли жорий этиш ягона меъёрий-ҳуқуқий база, институционал мустақиллик, рақамли воситалар, кадрлар тайёрғарлиги ва ривожланган этик маданият мавжудлигига боғлиқ. Мақолада халқаро стандартлар (ISO 37001, коррупцияга қарши конвенциялар, Европа Иттифоқи тажрибаси)ни миллий шарт-шароитларга мослаштириш зарурлиги таъкидланади. Хулоса қилинадики, норматив-ҳуқуқий мустаҳкамлаш, комплаенс механизмларини институционаллаштириш, кадрлар салоҳияти ва рақамли платформаларни ривожлантириш, ҳуқуқий онг ва ахлоқий мотивацияни ошириш Ўзбекистонда барқарор ва самарали комплаенс назорати тизимини шакллантиришнинг асосий шартларидир.

Калит сўзлар: комплаенс назорати, коррупцияга қарши курашиш, ҳуқуқий маданият, рақамлаштириш, институционал механизмлар, Ўзбекистон Республикаси.

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ПРОБЛЕМЫ ДЕЙСТВУЮЩЕЙ СИСТЕМЫ КОМПЛАЕНС-КОНТРОЛЯ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена анализу современного состояния системы комплаенс-контроля в Республике Узбекистан в контексте противодействия коррупции. Автор выделяет ключевые проблемы, ограничивающие эффективность действующей модели: отсутствие единого кодифицированного закона о комплаенсе, институциональная слабость подразделений и отсутствие методологий внутреннего контроля, кадровый дефицит специалистов, недостаточный уровень цифровизации процессов, а также низкая правовая культура и восприятие комплаенса в обществе. На основе сравнительного анализа с зарубежной практикой (США, Великобритания, Франция, Германия, Сингапур, Япония) показано, что успешность внедрения комплаенс-систем обеспечивается наличием единой нормативной базы, институциональной независимости, цифровых инструментов, профессиональной подготовки кадров и развитой этической культуры. В статье подчёркивается необходимость адаптации международных стандартов (ISO 37001, антикоррупционные конвенции, опыт ЕС) к национальным условиям. Сделан вывод о том, что нормативное укрепление, институционализация комплаенс-механизмов, развитие кадрового потенциала и цифровых платформ, а также повышение правосознания и этической мотивации являются ключевыми условиями для формирования устойчивой и эффективной системы комплаенс-контроля в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: комплаенс-контроль, противодействие коррупции, правовая культура, цифровизация, институциональные механизмы, Республика Узбекистан.

Despite certain successes in forming the regulatory and institutional infrastructure for compliance control, the current system in the Republic of Uzbekistan still faces a number of challenges that limit its effectiveness and sustainability. These challenges are legal, organizational, institutional, and cultural in nature.

Firstly, the country lacks a “comprehensive systemic law on compliance control” that would cover both the private and public sectors. The current regulations are fragmented and departmental, leading to varying interpretations of key concepts, duplication of functions, and weak integration of compliance into the overall risk management system. Without a codified approach, it is impossible to build a stable control hierarchy and ensure legal certainty.

At present, relevant norms are scattered across various legal acts – the Law “On Combating Corruption,” Presidential decrees, Cabinet of Ministers resolutions, as well as in internal documents of ministries and organizations. This approach results in several serious drawbacks. Different agencies and organizations interpret the term “compliance” in different ways: some see it solely as anti-corruption control, others as part of internal auditing, and still others as a system of ethics and conduct. This hinders the unification of approaches, complicates the training of specialists, and disorients law enforcement practitioners.

Without a dedicated law, it is impossible to create a standardized compliance architecture with mandatory components: risk assessment, reporting channels, internal investigation systems, disciplinary procedures, audit and reporting mechanisms. Currently, these elements are being implemented sporadically, without methodological support or proper oversight from authorized bodies.

The absence of a unified law leads to a low level of legal protection for compliance officers and whistleblowers. Their legal status is not defined, making them vulnerable to pressure and not guaranteeing their independence. In international practice, these aspects are strictly regulated, allowing for the effective protection of individuals who help uncover violations.

As a result, Uzbekistan is developing an asymmetrical and fragmented model of compliance control, where some organizations completely ignore the implementation of compliance mechanisms, while others act blindly, without regulatory guidance or methodological support. The introduction of a single law would help eliminate these disparities, establish core principles, tools, and procedures, and define the institutions responsible for implementation, control, monitoring, and system development.

The creation of such a law could be based on international standards like ISO 37001, provisions of anti-corruption conventions, and EU practices, adapted to Uzbekistan’s legal and institutional framework. It is important that this law does not duplicate existing regulations but serves as a coordinating legal act, ensuring integrity, enforceability, and sustainability of the compliance system.

Secondly, institutional mechanisms for compliance implementation remain underdeveloped. Despite the formal existence of units or responsible officers, in many organizations they exist only nominally, without real authority or support from management. There is no methodology for assessing their effectiveness, or for regular internal audits and monitoring. This turns compliance into a formality rather than a functional anti-corruption tool.

Institutional mechanisms play a key role in the effective implementation of compliance, ensuring a structured and systematic integration of regulatory requirements into the operations of organizations. These mechanisms include the development and implementation of policies, procedures, training programs, and monitoring systems aimed at ensuring compliance with legislation and internal standards.

Professor James T. Kobel emphasizes that effective compliance mechanisms must be integrated into the overall management strategy of the organization, ensuring alignment between departments and leadership[1]. Katharina Pfeil, Sarah Necker, and Lars Feld, based on their study of German institutions, concluded that the presence of an internal compliance system and regular employee training significantly increase the level of adherence to legal and ethical standards[2].

According to a review by Infonetica, 60% of research institutions reported difficulties in maintaining regulatory compliance amid rapidly changing regulations, highlighting the need for continuous adaptation and improvement of compliance infrastructure[3].

For Uzbekistan, these findings are particularly relevant. Effective implementation of institutional compliance mechanisms is possible under the following conditions:

- the establishment of specialized compliance units with the status of structural divisions;
- legal obligations codified for risk assessment, internal audits, and reporting;
- the development of training and certification programs for compliance officers;
- the introduction of digital platforms for internal control and communication;
- the formation of an ethical corporate culture focused on adherence to standards and transparency.

Scientific research and international practice show that the institutional strength of compliance is determined not only by a solid regulatory framework but also by the systematic implementation of these norms at the levels of governance, operations, and personnel training. Adapting these approaches to Uzbekistan’s national context can significantly enhance the effectiveness of anti-corruption control and build public trust in institutions.

Thirdly, a shortage of qualified personnel persists: there is a lack of specialists with knowledge in law, anti-corruption expertise, risk management, ethics, and digital technologies. Uzbekistan currently lacks national certification programs, university-level training modules, and established professional compliance officer communities. This hinders both the implementation and further development of compliance systems.

One of the key barriers to effective compliance control implementation in the Republic of Uzbekistan is this acute talent shortage. The lack of qualified professionals complicates both the introduction and ongoing development of compliance programs in the public and private sectors.

According to Professor Hans-Günter Schmidt of the International Anti-Corruption Academy, "compliance is not merely a regulatory process, but a competence that requires an interdisciplinary approach, legal training, and knowledge of psychology, management, and ethics"[4].

The lack of specialists with such a profile threatens the functioning of even the most advanced programs.

According to estimates by the WHO and the World Bank, in countries with transitional economies, including Uzbekistan, the share of personnel receiving regular training in internal control and ethics is less than 10% of the total workforce—significantly below international standards[5].

In Uzbekistan, compliance has not yet gained significant traction in higher legal education. Most universities do not offer specialized courses or training programs for compliance officers. Certification mechanisms and professional associations that support ongoing professional development are also lacking.

The absence of institutional support plays a detrimental role as well. There is no national center for training and retraining personnel in the field of compliance. As a result, companies and institutions are forced either to adapt untrained staff or to operate without compliance specialists altogether—reducing the effectiveness and reliability of internal anti-corruption mechanisms.

The staffing issue is an integral part of building a sustainable compliance system. Without proper training and continuous development of professionals, it is impossible to ensure either regulatory compliance or the establishment of a culture of accountability and ethical conduct.

Fourthly, the insufficient digitalization of compliance processes remains a pressing issue. In many agencies and companies, compliance is not integrated into electronic document management systems, risk assessment tools are not used, and reporting of violations is carried out manually, without guarantees of confidentiality.

Digitalization of compliance processes in Uzbekistan is still in its early stages, significantly limiting the effectiveness of anti-corruption control. Given the increasing complexity of business processes, the volume of information, and growing demands for transparency, the lack of modern digital tools renders the compliance function formal and reactive, rather than proactive and analytically driven.

In most public and private organizations, the compliance system is not integrated into the digital infrastructure. Oversight is conducted manually, data is collected on paper, and reports of violations are submitted through unsecured or informal channels. This not only reduces response efficiency but also increases the risks of data leaks, manipulation, and retaliatory actions against whistleblowers.

In countries such as Singapore, South Korea, and Estonia, government agencies and state-owned enterprises use platforms integrated with AI and Big Data to assess corruption risks and conduct automated procurement audits. In Germany and the Netherlands, companies are required to document key actions in digital environments for subsequent compliance auditing.

Uzbekistan currently lacks a national standard or software solution for digital compliance. This results in fragmentation and distrust, and makes centralized monitoring of compliance effectiveness impossible. Considering the existing platforms for electronic procurement (etender.uz), digital document management (dxarid.uz), and fiscal systems, the state possesses the technical potential to transition to electronic compliance tools.

Digitalization not only simplifies processes but enables the shift toward intelligent compliance, where monitoring occurs in real time and the prevention of violations becomes the primary function of the system, rather than a byproduct.

Fifth, there is a low level of legal culture and limited perception of compliance as an institutional value. In many cases, employees view anti-corruption procedures as an “additional burden” rather than an element of professional ethics. There is no system of incentives and rewards for ethical behavior, nor are there role models or positive success stories in the public sphere.

Building an effective compliance control system is impossible without a strong legal culture, a recognition of rules as binding, and a deeply rooted anti-corruption ethic within society. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, this aspect remains one of the most underdeveloped and vulnerable.

Despite recent reforms, a significant number of employees in both the public and private sectors still perceive compliance as a formality—something done solely to meet reporting requirements. The absence of internal motivation and a lack of understanding of compliance as a self-regulatory tool leads to low engagement, resistance to new procedures, and a greater susceptibility to corrupt practices.

A study by Deloitte revealed that in countries with a high level of legal culture, over 70% of employees believe that violating compliance policies will lead to consequences. In countries with low institutional trust, this figure does not exceed 25% [6]. This directly affects the effectiveness of violation detection, the execution of internal investigations, and the level of participation in compliance programs.

In Uzbekistan, there are still no systemic public education campaigns focused on compliance awareness. Public discussions, examples of successful detection and prevention of violations, and the involvement of civil society in monitoring ethics and transparency are all in a nascent stage. Within universities and the business community, compliance is still largely seen as a “bureaucratic imposition”.

Without a shift in public and professional perception, compliance programs risk remaining externally impressive but internally ineffective. Therefore, improving legal culture is not a secondary task—it is a core element of successful anti-corruption policy.

Practice shows that unless the above-mentioned issues are addressed, the current compliance control system will not be able to fulfill its anti-corruption function effectively. Legal reinforcement, institutionalization of best practices, professionalization of the workforce, the adoption of digital solutions, and the cultivation of a culture of lawful and ethical conduct at all levels of governance are all essential.

An analysis of the existing compliance control system in the Republic of Uzbekistan reveals a range of systemic and structural issues that hinder its effective operation and development. Chief among them is the absence of a unified, codified law on compliance control, which would define principles, mechanisms, and standards for both the public and private sectors. The current fragmented and agency-specific regulations create legal uncertainty and hinder the unification of approaches.

Institutional instability also remains a serious obstacle: in most cases, compliance units lack both real autonomy and sufficient authority. The absence of evaluation methodologies, internal audit systems, and performance monitoring renders the control function largely formal[7-10]. The talent shortage further exacerbates the issue: a lack of qualified specialists, underdeveloped educational programs, and no certification mechanisms make it impossible to implement compliance functions effectively in practice.

In addition, digitalization remains insufficient, limiting transparency, responsiveness, and resilience in oversight. In a time of digital transformation, neither the state nor businesses can effectively manage compliance risks without the use of digital platforms, automated monitoring tools, and secure whistleblowing channels.

Perhaps the most fundamental barrier is the low level of legal culture and perception of compliance. Without an understanding of its importance, without internal ethical motivation and a genuine commitment to rule-following, even the most advanced procedures will fail. Formality, cynicism toward anti-corruption mechanisms, and fear of retaliation—rather than trust and transparency—highlight the urgent need for a deep cultural transformation.

The comparative analysis conducted has shown that foreign jurisdictions have made significant progress in the institutionalization and standardization of compliance. Leading examples in this area include the United States, the United Kingdom, France, Singapore, Japan, and Germany, where compliance control is an integral part of the corporate, administrative, and legal environments. Key elements of successful compliance implementation in these countries include: a unified regulatory framework, institutional independence, digitalization of processes, professional training of personnel, and a strong perception of compliance as an ethical and social value.

In contrast, the current system in Uzbekistan is characterized by fragmentation, weak integration into management processes, a shortage of trained personnel, limited digitalization, and a low level of trust in compliance mechanisms. The absence of a codified approach, effective internal and external oversight mechanisms, and a persistent culture of formalism significantly undermine the overall effectiveness of anti-corruption policies.

Thus, the effective adaptation of international practices, the removal of institutional and regulatory barriers, and the development of a legal and ethical culture are essential conditions for building a mature and effective model of compliance control in the national context.

The study has revealed that the existing compliance control system in Uzbekistan is fragmented and institutionally weak, which severely limits its potential in combating corruption. The absence of a unified systemic law and methodological framework, the shortage of qualified personnel, and the low level of digitalization pose significant obstacles to the integration of compliance into management practices. Additionally, the low level of legal culture and the formal perception of compliance hinder the establishment of a sustainable anti-corruption environment.

The effective development of the national system is possible only through the adaptation of international standards and best practices, institutional strengthening of compliance units, professional training of specialists, the implementation of digital monitoring tools, and the cultivation of both corporate and societal ethical culture. Only a comprehensive approach to these challenges will allow Uzbekistan to build a mature and effective compliance control model based on the principles of legality, transparency, and trust.

References/Иқтибослар/Сноски:

1. James T. Kobel. Institutional Compliance Strategies in Higher Education – Journal of College and University Law. – Vol. 44. 2018. – С. 85
2. Pfeil K., Necker S. Compliance Management in Research Institutions. – Freiburg Economic Papers. 2023. – С. 91
3. Infonetica. Research Governance and Compliance in 2023. URL: www.infonetica.net
4. Schmidt H.G. Compliance as Interdisciplinary Governance – IACA Lecture Series. 2021. – С. 211

5. World Bank. Public Sector Training Capacity in Transition Economies. 2022. – С. 74
6. Deloitte. Global Compliance Survey. 2022. URL: www2.deloitte.com
7. Saparovna N. S. et al. Issues of Criminal Liability for Suicide //Journal of Ecohumanism. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 8. – С. 11559-11568.
8. Khamidov N. CRIMINAL-LEGAL ASPECTS OF THE DRUG ABUSE IN SOME COUNTRIES AND IMPOSED APPROACHES AGAINST IT //International Journal of Legal Studies (IJOLS). – 2018. – Т. 4. – С. 177-182.
9. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=bvK4GS0AAAAJ&citation_for_view=bvK4GS0AAAAJ:eQOLeE2rZwMC
10. Saparovna, N. S., Allanova, A., Khamidov, N., Sunnatov, V., Toshev, O., & Gazibekov, K. (2025). Criminal Law Description of Domestic Violence. Journal of Ecohumanism, 4(2), 2004-2016.

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